

Thiền viện Trúc Lâm Bình Phước

also known as “Bamboo Grove Thiền Monastery, Bình Phước”

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Entry tags: Temple, Religious Group, Buddhist Traditions, Drukpa Kagyu, Language, Tibetan Buddhist Traditions, Religious Place, Vietnamese Buddhist Traditions, Thiền phái Trúc Lâm (Bamboo Grove School), Thiền phái Trúc Lâm (Bamboo Grove School), Vietnamese Religions, Thiền Buddhism (Vietnamese Chan), Thiền Buddhism, Austroasiatic, Vietic

Thiền viện Trúc Lâm Bình Phước (translated into English as “Bamboo Grove Thiền Monastery, Bình Phước”) is located in a commune in Bình Phước province adjacent to the Cambodia border. The temple is closely associated with the Tibetan Drukpa lineage, founded by Naropa over 1,000 years ago. The temple occasionally hosts Drukpa monks (largely from Ladakh) to host Tibetan ceremonies and empowerments while visiting Vietnam. This entry is based on ethnographic fieldwork conducted in 2023 at Quan Âm Tu Viện, which is the mother temple of Thiền viện Trúc Lâm Bình Phước, and in January 2024, during the visit of Gyalwa Dokhampa and about 25 Drukpa monks, during which time they conducted a well-attended ‘Kilaya Fire puja’ and ‘Drolma Yuldok’ ritual of 21 Taras to remove obstacles and bring about auspiciousness. The temple is a nunnery. The land on which the temple is built was part of Căn cứ Tà Thiết, a major battlefield and military base that the National Liberation Front of Southern Vietnam (NLF, Mặt trận Dân tộc Giải phóng miền Nam Việt Nam) launched their participation for the Spring 1975 General Offensive (Tổng tiến công và nổi dậy mùa Xuân 1975). It is colloquially referred to as a “red address” (địa chỉ đỏ)—a revolutionary site allied with the Communist Party and against the American and South Vietnamese governments. It is part of official nationalist historical reclamation projects (Grossheim 2018). As a former battlefield, it is believed by the local people to be a place of restless ghosts and spirits associated with dead soldiers. As part of the military base’s renovation, Bình Phước Province People’s Committee allocated 60 hectares of land to build Thiền viện Trúc Lâm Bình Phước. The construction began in late 2017 and was completed in early 2020. In 2020, the monastery contained a Mahayana-style main hall, Nhà Địa Tạng (Kṣitigarbha shrine room), Nhà Linh (an outside shrine dedicated to local spirits and dead soldiers), a communal kitchen and residential quarters for nuns. A local business, Đại Nam Joint Stock Company, donated 50 billion VND to the construction of the temple. Its subsidiary company, Đại Nam Bình Dương Construction Company Limited, constructed the temple. Upon completion, the Venerable (Thượng Tọa) Thích Thanh Phong, the standing member of the Central Executive Council of the Vietnam Buddhist Sangha (VBS), and the abbot at Vĩnh Nghiêm temple in Hồ Chí Minh City (HCMC), appointed Thích Nữ Huệ Đức, the current abbot at Quan Âm Tu Viện, a syncretic Mahayana-Vajrayana temple in Ho Chi Minh City, to be the abbot of this newly built temple. Thiền viện Trúc Lâm Bình Phước epitomizes Tibeto-Vietnamese syncretism in aesthetics, rituals and teachings. In 2023, the temple constructed a cluster of 15 Tibetan-style meditation villas for short and long-term Vajrayana retreat courses. It is being expanded to 25 villas. This entry focuses on the syncretic practices.

Date Range: 2017 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Bình Phước province

Region tags: Bình Phước, Southeast Asia, Vietnam

Bình Phước province touching the Cambodia border.

Status of Participants:

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Gyalwang Drukpa. 2015. Nghi quỹ tu trì giản lược Đức Lục Độ Phật Mẫu Tara [Abridged sadhana of Tara]. Hanoi: NXB Tôn giáo

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.facebook.com/quanamtuvien>
- Source 1 Description: Thiền viện Trúc Lâm Bình Phước shares the same abbot with Quan Âm Tu Viện, a nunnery in Hồ Chí Minh City that practices Tibeto-Vietnamese Buddhism. All events at Bình Phước are advertised and broadcasted on its sister temple's Facebook page.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.facebook.com/thienvientruclambinhphuc/>
- Source 2 Description: Facebook page of Thiền viện Trúc Lâm Bình Phước

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Tree, grove, or forest
- Other [specify]: A former military camp.

Notes: As a former military base, it is believed to have countless angry ghosts and spirits from war. It is partially for this reason that Tibetan Drukpa monks are invited to help pacify the land.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Clearing
- Trackway or road-surface
- Water feature
- Plantings

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Notes: Thiền viện Trúc Lâm Bình Phước is located in Lộc Thịnh commune (xã), Lộc Ninh district (huyện), Bình Phước Province (tỉnh). The commune is adjacent to the Cambodia border to the west.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ A single structure

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: There are several features.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The main hall, residential area, kitchen, and Nhà Địa Tạng (a shrine dedicated to the Bodhisattva King Kṣitigarbha and local spirits) were built in 2017 and completed in 2020. After receiving the temple, the current abbot, Thích Nữ Huệ Đức, built a cluster of meditation villas in a modern Tibetan style, with Tibetan ritual objects inside each. The villas construction started in 2023 and is ongoing. The temple is fascinating because

leaders are consciously but quietly shifting the ritual capacities towards Drukpa practice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The meditation villas are built and decorated in Tibetan style. The meditation park is built in Japanese style with a torii at the entrance. Other structures reflect typical Vietnamese Mahayana aesthetics.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Notes: It is the site of many visits and empowerments from Tibetan monks.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– No

Notes: The entire temple complex is located on a 60 hectare piece of land. The temple has plans to expand constructions in the future after raising sufficient funding.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: The place worships Trần Nhân Tông (1258-1308), the founder of the Bamboo Grove school in Vietnamese Buddhism. He was a Trần Dynasty (1226-1400) King before becoming a Buddhist monk. He received the title "Phật Hoàng" (Royal Buddha) for defending the country from the Mongolian invasion and reached enlightenment in Yên Tử Mountain. However, there is also a growing Tibeto-Vietnamese aspect that incorporates Tibetan Buddhism.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: Inside the Kṣitigarbha building are altars that worship “hương linh ông bà tiên chủ đất” (ancestral spirits of the place), “hương linh thập loại cô hồn” (spirits of ten types of ghosts), “Thần linh Tà Thiết” (Gods/Protectors of Tà Thiết) and “Hương linh chư vị tôn thần” (spirits of deities). The center altar is dedicated to the Bodhisattva King Kṣitigarbha.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The land was allocated to temple construction by the chairman of the Bình Phước's People's Committee. He personally raised donations from provincial businesses and individuals for construction. Đại Nam Joint Stock Company donated 50 billion VND and a

branch of this same company (Đại Nam Bình Dương Construction Company Limited) was responsible for constructing the temple.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

– Other [specify]: Đại Nam Bình Dương Construction Company Limited

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Notes: The temple is located in Lộc Ninh district, Bình Phước province on the piece of land that is part of Căn cứ Tà Thiết (Tà Thiết Military Base). It was used as a military base during the wars against the French and Americans, and was one of the largest gathering points for communist soldiers who marched southward from the north to prepare for the General offensive and uprising in 1975 (Tổng tiến công và nổi dậy mùa Xuân 1975) or often referred to as the Ho Chi Minh Campaign. The entire area was former battlefields and is believed to be the place of dead soldiers' spirits.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– No

Notes: The land was allocated to temple construction by the chairman of the Bình Phước's People's Committee. He personally raised donations from provincial businesses and individuals for construction. Đại Nam Joint Stock Company donated 50 billion VND and a branch of this same company (Đại Nam Bình Dương Construction Company Limited) was responsible for constructing the temple.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

– Other [specify]: To liberate the dead soldiers' spirits in Tà Thiết area.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: There is an artificial canal that runs around the temple complex.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The main hall is central for ritual purposes. Also, the largest meditation villa, used by The Ninth Gyalwa Dokhampa during events, is central among all the Tibetan-style meditation villas.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Earth

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Sand

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Clay

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Plaster

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Wood

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Grass

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Stone

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: The construction uses traditional concrete.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: Faded printed Mahayana-style depictions of Bodhisattvas and the Buddha are on all the outside walls.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: There are murals of different bodhisattvas and buddhas on the wall and ceiling of the main hall.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: There are large-size printed images of different Bodhisattvas and Buddhas in Vietnamese Mahayana style hanging both inside and outside of the main hall. During the dharma event hosted by Gyalwa Dokhampa, color printed posters and flyers hung ubiquitously around the temple complex, advertising for the event. Inside the Tibetan-style meditation villas are decorated with Tibetan thangkas and statues. The temple exemplifies a space that has a growing degree of Tibeto-Vietnamese religious practice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: On the ceiling of the main hall is a mural depicting dragons flying on white clouds against the backdrop of a blue sky.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: For example, dharmachakras and swastikas.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

Notes: Tibetan-style decorations in the meditation villas are restricted from view by being placed across an artificial canal, and only available to select Vajrayana followers mostly associated with Quan Âm Tu Viện.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Cult statues:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Inside the main hall are statues of Amitabha, Samantabhadra, and Manjushri. Nhà Địa Tạng has the Bodhisattva King Kṣitigarbha statue on the center altar. Nhà Thờ Tổ has the center statue of Phật Hoàng Trần Nhân Tông, and his two disciples on the sides. Inside each Tibetan-style villa is a Vajrayana-style statue of Avalokiteshvara on the small altar.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Statues of humans:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

Notes: There are many wall paintings. In the front of the main hall, where the three main statues are, there are paintings of each deity behind the statue, creating a doubling effect.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: During the Vajrayana rituals and empowerments hosted by the Ninth Gyalwa Dokhampa, Tibetan-style statues are brought into the mainhall and placed on both the main altar and smaller temporary altars.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: On the ceiling is a painted depiction of dragons and clouds.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Notes: While the iconography is all relatively standard for Buddhism, what is unique about this temple is the juxtaposition and hybridity of the iconography. It typifies a small but growing trend for Mahayana temples to have strong Vajrayana iconographic elements, mixed in together. It is the recombination that is notable and constitutes a "distinct feature". In this case, it is notable how Tibetan Vajrayana elements are often segregated onto the more recently built meditation villa area, and the main hall is primarily in Vietnamese Mahayana style except for when hosting Drukpa ritual events.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

Notes: Tibetan statues are made in a stylized fashion normal for the region.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Various deities and dharma protectors take human form.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: These includes vajras, swastikas, mudras and dharmachakras.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Humans

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Narrative murals of the life of Buddha.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Human narratives

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

Notes: Because this temple is situated on the area of an intense battlefield, and discursively framed as a heritage site as a 'red address', it is a place of worship with strong undertones of placating spirits (e.g., the outside shrine and bamboo cluster that is the active site of ghosts, assiduously avoided by most nuns). The temple has a Kṣitigarbha building dedicated to the worship of different local spirits and war heroes, such as “hương linh ông bà tiền chủ đất” (spirits of previous landowners), “hương linh thập loại cô hồn” (spirits of ten types of ghost), “Thần linh Tà Thiết” (Gods/Protectors of Tà Thiết), “Hương linh chư vị tôn thần” (spirits of deities), and “anh hùng liệt sỹ, chiến sỹ trận vong, đồng bào tử nạn” (war heroes, soldiers who died in battle, and war victims). We did fieldwork there during a Drukpa event that brought prominent Tibetan monks to the temple. Among their various activities was an event to pacify lingering spirits.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– Yes

Notes: For example, Phật Hoàng Trần Nhân Tông.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Are formal burials present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: There is no supreme god within the panoply of Buddhism.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Notes: Tà Thiết area was a former military base and battlefield. The local people believe that the place is filled with wandering spirits from the war.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Nhà Linh is a colloquial name for a small shrine built by construction workers behind Nhà Địa Tạng. It is believed by the resident nuns that the specific spot is filled with dead soldier spirits. The managing director of the temple, a former communist fighter from the north, is among only people who feel comfortable to visit the shrine area, since the ghosts are largely of his departed comrades.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Human spirits can be physically felt to some people. We heard a story of a nun being pressed down to the bed by a dark shadow and she could feel the spirit's weight on her. And

other nuns reported feeling human spirits around an outside shrine.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

Notes: A straightforward example of this are tulkus or reincarnated lamas.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Drukpa tulkus and rinpoches, as examples of mixed human-divine beings, frequent the temple and communicate with followers both in directly and through supernatural means.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ In trance possession:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Libations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Offerings of food:

–Yes [specify]: tsok - an important Vajrayana practice of offering food and drink. Every noon, before having the lunch, the nuns would do food offering to Đại bàng Kim Sí Điểu (Garuda).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ **Animal sacrifice:**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ **Human sacrifice:**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ **Sacred objects:**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ **Daily life objects:**

– Yes [specify]: Food, clothing and daily essentials.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ **Other:**

– Other [specify]: N/a

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ **Supernatural beings care about sex:**

– Yes

Notes: Similar to its sister temple, Quan Âm Tu Viện, in Hồ Chí Minh City, this temple is popular among LGBTQ+ followers as they share the same pool of follower demographics. However, the temple does not openly support queer sexuality.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ **Does the worship include sex acts/references:**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

Notes: Construction workers and gardeners working at the temple are believed to be good people because they have been spiritually selected by the spirits and protectors of the temple. But in instances where workers have stolen money left by followers on dishes in the shrine, they are punished with physical ailments. There are two cases of workers who stole money and later both got into horrible accidents. One broke his arm and the other had a major concussion. Greedy and disrespectful employees are cast with spells to leave the temple on their own and never to come back again.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Visitors to temple experience spiritual connection with deities and spirits.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Large-scale rituals are empowerments hosted by Tibetan monks from the Drukpa lineage that tend to attract hundreds of participants.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Small-scale rituals are everyday's chanting. Nuns at Thiền viện Trúc lâm Bình Phước practice both Mahayana and Vajrayana (Tịnh-Mật song tu). The temple has a daily schedule for Mahayana services twice in a day. The morning chanting session starts from 4-6am with Śūraṅgama Sūtra. The evening chanting session starts from 6-8pm with Lotus Sutra (Saddharma Puṇḍarīka Sūtram, Sūtra on the White Lotus of the True Dharma), Kṣitigarbha Bodhisattva Pūrvapraṇidhāna Sutra or Confession Sutra. The evening chanting session usually attracts local residents.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 300

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Large-scale rituals only take place whenever the Drukpa lineage comes to the temple. Small-scale rituals take place daily at the temple main hall.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The abbot, Thích Nữ Huệ Đức, is the student of the Venerable Thích Viên Thành - the 11th Head of Tổ đình Hương Tích or Chùa Hương, and Gyalwang Drukpa of Tibetan Buddhism, maintains orthodoxy and orthopraxy checks on Mahayana and Tibetan rituals at the temple.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The abbot, Thích nữ Huệ Đức, is the student of the Venerable Thích Viên Thành - the 11th Head of Tổ đình Hương Tích or Chùa Hương, and Gyalwang Drukpa of Tibetan Buddhism, maintains orthodoxy and orthopraxy checks on Mahayana and Tibetan rituals at the temple.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: As described above, this is a syncretistic Tibeto-Vietnamese temple.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: Donations come in different forms: dropping cash inside donation boxes, food and flower offerings. For corporate followers, they tend to donate to the construction or event organization at the temple.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/a

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Notes: Cooking and cleaning are done by resident nuns, with the help of volunteers during major events. The temple has its own group of gardeners that plant flowers and take care of the outdoor space.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: There are no formal pilgrimages that begin or end at the temple. However, Drukpa followers shadow the sangha around the country when they come, and one of the stops is Thiền viện Trúc Lâm Bình Phước. This does not constitute formal pilgrimage practices endorsed by temple leadership.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Notes: Feasting is typical of many Mahayana temples in Vietnam, where after a ritual event there is a free meal. The food is always vegetarian. For instance, during the four-day event hosted Gyalwa Dokhampa, food and shelter were provided for all participants.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Priests

– Yes

Notes: Nuns

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Local elites

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Private contributions

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: Feasting is held at the dining hall, right in front of the kitchen.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Notes: For Mahayana, festival is organized during the month of Vesak and includes Buddha showering ceremony and sutra recitation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: annually

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: 500

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Religious professionals

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Notes: Healing is not a part of the temple's permanent practice, but when Gyalwa Dokhampa came in January 2024, he handed out barley flour dough, or tsampa, to participants and instructed them roll over their bodies to pick up all the toxicity and ailments. The tsampa balls were later collected and destroyed. We talked to a volunteer who attended last year and experienced cures from the same ritual.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Notes: The temple has six to ten permanent resident nuns, who are frequently rotated with other nuns at Quan Âm Tu Viện. Younger and newly ordained nuns often stay in Quan Âm Tu Viện because they have to finish their bachelor's degree at Vietnam Buddhist University. Nuns living in Bình Phước tend to be older and have already completed their studies.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Thiền viện Trúc Lâm Bình Phước is a nunnery with all religious specialists are female.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

Notes: It is common for nuns to live in a temple for life. However, they might receive reallocation order to serve as abbots of other temples in the future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The temple has dedicated infrastructure for permanent residence. It also provides residence for nuns and followers who want to go on retreat. There is a senior nun who is doing a three-year Tibetan Buddhist retreat (in the style started by Jamgon Kongtrul Lodrö Taye in the 19th century).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The temple offers both short and long-term retreat for religious specialists and lay people.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: As the temple is an official member of the Vietnam Buddhist Sangha (VBS), it is under the supervision and management of VBS Bình Phước.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Notes: Even though the temple is under the administrative monitoring of the Vietnam Buddhist Sangha (VBS), there is no formal bureaucracy at the temple. The abbot, Thích Nữ Huệ Đức, is a member of the Chief Secretary of the Central Nunnery Division of VBS.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: According to the Vietnam Buddhist Sangha (VBS) Charter (revised in 2022), temples have legal rights to land and donation usage (Chapter VIII, Article 55).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Notes: Primary income of the temple comes from donations. The new Circular No. 04/2023/TT-BTC on Guidelines for Management, Collection and Use of funding for organization of festivals and religious donations or grants for relic sites and festivities issued on January 19, 2023 regulates donations of all religious sites in Vietnam. According to the circular, religious institutions are required to open a deposit account at either the State Treasury or a commercial

bank to keep record of the money donated through wire transfers. Cash donations are required to be counted weekly and deposited to the opened bank account. Each religious institution is expected to produce annual financial reports, but not required to submit to any state agencies. Individual temples and pagodas are still responsible for their own donation collection, management and usage.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: The temple has an office that handles administrative works. Non-religious records and documents are stored here. In addition, according to the new Circular No. 04/2023/TT-BTC on Guidelines for Management, Collection and Use of funding for organization of festivals and religious donations or grants for relic sites and festivities issued on January 19, 2023, religious institutions are expected to produce annual financial reports, but not required to submit to any state agencies. These records are stored in the office within the temple premise.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Bình Phước